

Use of Social Media Sites for Collaborative Learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities.

¹Robert, Prudencia S., ²Miwari, Goodluck U. PhD, & ¹Prof. Ubulom, W. J.

¹Department of Business Education

²Department of Educational Foundations

Faculty of Education, Rivers State University

Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Corresponding Authors' Email: robertprudencia8@gmail.com; goodluck.miwari@ust.edu.ng

Abstract

This study examined the use of Social Media Sites for Collaborative Learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities. It specifically determined the extent to which Facebook, WhatsApp, You Tube and Twitter groups are used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities. Four research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study which adopted descriptive survey design. The total population of 91 Postgraduate Business Education Students from the two River State owned Universities was used as sample size since it was a managerial size. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured 20-item Questionnaire titled "Use of Social Media Sites for Collaborative Learning" (USMSCL). Validated by two experts in Business Education and one in Measurement and Evaluation, the instrument has a reliability coefficient of 0.72 which was established using Cronbach's Alpha model. Data was analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while T-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that Social Media Sites enhance student's active learning and enable them to share learning resources, information, and discussions effectively. However, some sites were found to be utilized to a low extent for collaborative learning. Based on the findings, it was recommended amongst others that orientation programmes should be carried out to create more awareness among Business Education students in general, on the usefulness of Social Media Sites.

Keywords. Business Education, Collaborative Learning, Postgraduate Students, Social Media Sites.

INTRODUCTION

The advancement of technology in education is so captivating and the ability to integrate the social media in the learning process, sharing ideas and interact with one another is something very interesting. The learner's attitude is vital with respect to collaborative learning, and this is particularly dependent on his perception of social media-based collaborative learning (SMBCL). Usually though, it is observed that students' attitude toward collaborative learning is positive. Collaborative learning with social media sites helps to inculcate communication skills, teamwork and problem-solving skills in students. The ability to collaborate and solve problems among students, leads to the concept of collaborative learning.

Collaborative learning is an educational approach to teaching and learning that involves group of learners working together to solve a problem, complete tasks, or create a product and achieve common learning goals. Collaborative learning increase student retention, self-esteem, builds relationships, encourages engagement, improves confidence, creates trust, inspires creativity, and promotes diversity. It can lead to significant retention and the capability to apply knowledge novelly. Essential skills like critical thinking, communication, problem-solving, and teamwork can be developed through collaborative learning (Wagino, Maksum, Purwanto, Krismadinata, Suhendar, & Koto (2023). Collaboration is achieved in learning by dividing students into groups or assigning them to work in order to achieve a goal in a research or discovery/ inquiry process (Khan, 2019).

Collaborative learning with social media site has an effective impact on student engagement and learning performance. Social Media Site is defined as interactive technologies that facilitate the creation, sharing, and aggregation of content, ideas, interests, and other forms of expression through virtual communities

and networks. It enables users to interact with the members of their networks using different communication tools; its spark affects completely every aspect of our life: communication, employment, politics, healthcare, social relationships, personal productivity, businesses and most importantly, education and learning (Sadiku, Omotoso, & Musa, 2019).

Business Education as defined by Ubulom and Dambo (2016), is an educational training directed towards equipping individuals with business and vocational skills, while Akpomi & Kayii (2020), view Business Education programme as a structure to give students training that will develop their abilities, skills, and expose them to vocational opportunities. On their part, Ogwunte and Ile (2017) conceive Business Education as that aspect of the total educational programme that provides the knowledge, skills, understanding and attitude needed to perform in the business world as a producer or consumer of goods and services that business offer. Amadi (2021) perceived Business Education as a formidable force in equipping youths with appropriate skills, knowledge, abilities and competencies to enable the individual to be self-employed and self-reliant leading to sustainable economic growth and poverty eradication in the society.

Social Media Sites connect individuals on different features for academic purposes to achieve a collaborative knowledge where group of learners can communicate, discuss, learn, process, share, solve problems to achieve educational goals and objectives. Yet most learners fail to appreciate the importance and values of social media sites for academic purposes, and this is a challenge which the researchers attempt to address particularly among Postgraduate students in Rivers State Universities. Social Media Sites considered in the study are Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, and Twitter.

Facebook for Collaborative Learning

Facebook is a social media site that makes it easy for users to connect with friends, families, colleagues or people online and also helps to share videos, articles thoughts, and opinions with one another. Facebook is one of the popular platforms used for learning support tools (Aleksandrova & Parusheva, 2019). Affirming that the most widely used tool for academic-related communication is Facebook, Radwan et al. (2020), emphasized that Facebook is the most commonly used social media platform among students, and has proven to be the most popular among students for its ease of use.

WhatsApp for Collaborative Learning

WhatsApp is a Social Media Site that enables connection with people utilizing their smartphones. WhatsApp became one of the applications that were often used for learning activities (Kapasia et al. (2020). So used is WhatsApp in learning to support discussion and facilitate interaction and exchange of information in several media formats that it is increasingly becoming popular among students (Manca, 2020). It is a good medium for collaborative learning as it allows users to send instant messages personally or in groups. Multimedia messages can also be shared among participants in a group or individually (Gon & Rawekar, 2017). WhatsApp as an application is popular among students and teachers (LaHanisi, Risdiany, DwiUtami & Sulisworo, 2018). WhatsApp group features allow up to 256 participants in a group (WhatsApp. Com, 2017). This makes it very convenient as the number of participants is high.

YouTube for Collaborative Learning

YouTube is a website for sharing videos. Users view, share, upload, comment on, like, or dislike videos on the platform. It is a good medium for collaborative learning as students and teachers spend time

watching YouTube videos which helps them to improve their listening comprehension and pronunciation skills. Users can 'like' content, interact with other users, and follow the channels that appeals to them (Awa-Abuon, 2021). It is the largest video-sharing platform around the world that gives users access to share personal or corporate video content (Vanguard), 2014). Its accessibility around the world encourages users to upload content as it will be viewed globally and this explains why there are various personal YouTube channels. According to Wikipedia, as of October 2020, YouTube has 2 billion users.

Twitter for Collaborative Learning

Twitter is a social media site that is drastically different from Facebook. It was created in 2006 by Jack Dorsey. Using Twitter for educational purposes makes users avoid cumbersome words and give a direct representation of points to be made thus enabling an explicit sharing of ideas. Interestingly, people from different spheres of life use Twitter to communicate. Authors like Naeem (2019), Seitz and Misra (2020), Amidi et al., (2017), Kayode et al. (2019), Cevik et al. (2016), and Irizarry (2020) highlighted many of the possible benefits of using Social Media Sites in education which include influencing the learning outcomes of the students, helping them attain social acceptance, helping them adapt to the university culture as well as enabling them to establish and maintain their relationships.

Statement of the Problem

Collaborative learning with social media sites plays an important role in the lives of students as it emphasizes teamwork and shared responsibilities among students. Unfortunately graduates who wants to further their education are often hindered by such factors like large class sizes, insufficient classrooms, lack of teachers trained on the use of modern technological tools and how to manage group activities. These students thus, find it difficult to participate actively with their course mates in solving complex problems and achieving a task, which limits the development of critical thinking, communication skills, teamwork and problem-solving skill.

The question of the best teaching-learning approach comes to mind and the readily considered approach is collaborative learning with social media sites for their flexibilities. With social media sites, students can be shared into groups and assigned knowledge-based tasks to achieve and also interact amongst themselves to learn, discuss, share ideas, share knowledge, and solve problems, as collaborative learning is an educational approach to teaching and learning that involves groups of learners working together to solve a problem, complete a task, or create a product.

Nevertheless, studies appear not to have paid sufficient attention to the relationship between the uses of social media sites for collaborative learning among business education Postgraduate students. It is on this note that the researcher intends to examine the use of social media sites for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate students in Rivers State Universities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine the extent to which Social Media Sites are used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. examine the extent to which Facebook group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities.

2. determine the extent to which WhatsApp group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities.
3. investigate the extent to which YouTube group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities.
4. determine the extent to which Twitter group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent do Business Education Postgraduate Students use Facebook group for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities?
2. To what extent do Business Education Postgraduate Students use WhatsApp group for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities?
3. To what extent do Business Education Postgraduate Students use YouTube group for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities?
4. To what extent do Business Education Postgraduate Students use Twitter group for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which Facebook group is used for collaborative learning.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which WhatsApp group is used for collaborative learning.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which YouTube group is used for collaborative learning.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which Twitter group is used for collaborative learning.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive Survey Research Design was adopted for the study which was carried out in Rives State. A state in the Niger Delta sub-region of the South-South geopolitical zones of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of 91 Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, for the 2022/2023 academic session, as shown in the population distribution below.

Table 1: Population Distribution of Postgraduate Business Education Students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education in 2022/2023 Session

2022/2023 Academic Session				
S/N	Institution	M.Sc	Ph.D	Total
1.	RSU	32	12	44
2	IAUE	36	11	47
	Grand Total	68	23	91

The entire population of 91 postgraduate students was used for the study. A 20-item structured questionnaire titled “Use of Social Media Sites for Collaborative Learning (USMSCL)” was used for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by experts in Business Education and Measurement and Evaluation from faculty of Education in Rivers State University. Cronbach Alpha statistical tool was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded a coefficient of 0.72. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A mean rating below 1.99 was considered low extent, between 2.00 to 2.99 moderate extent and 3.00 and above was considered as high extent. Observed t-values less than their critical equivalents led retaining of the stated null hypothesis, otherwise the null hypothesis was dropped and the alternative accepted.

RESULT

Research question 1: To what extent do Business Education Postgraduate Students use Facebook group for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Postgraduate Students of Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the Extent to which Business Education Postgraduate Students use Facebook group for Collaborative Learning.

S/N	Items	RSU (n = 44)			IAUE (n=47)			N = 91 Aggregate		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks.	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks.	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks.
1	Facebook group is used for collaborative learning by creating online groups for students to learn, ask questions and get feedback directly	2.76	1.07	ME	2.96	1.04	ME	2.86	1.06	ME
2	Students and lecturers can communicate with each other on Facebook group for collaborative learning and teaching	3.00	0.99	HE	3.17	0.54	HE	3.09	0.77	HE
3	Lecturers can share educational information to a large group of students on Facebook group for collaborative learning	2.97	1.06	ME	2.65	1.13	ME	2.81	1.10	ME
4	A large number of students through Facebook group can work together to solve a problem for collaborative learning.	3.21	1.05	HE	3.00	1.06	HE	3.11	1.06	HE
5	Facebook group is used for collaborative learning as it provides rich learning and teaching practices in informal learning context	3.15	1.08	HE	3.22	0.93	HE	3.19	1.01	HE
Grand Mean/SD		2.42	0.84	ME	2.47	0.71	ME	2.45	0.78	ME

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

Table 2 Shows the item-by-item analyses and grand mean ratings of postgraduate students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, respectively 2.42 (0.84) and 2.47 (0.71), while the aggregate grand mean is 2.45 (0.78) indicating that students of the two Universities agreed that to a

moderate extent, Facebook group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate student of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education.

Research Question 2: To what extent do Business Education Postgraduate Students use WhatsApp group for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Postgraduate Students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Students on the Extent to which WhatsApp group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students N = 91

S/N	Items	RSU (n = 44)			IAUE (n=47)			Aggregate		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
6	WhatsApp group is used for collaborative learning as it acts as a virtual extensions of classroom, allowing students and lecturers to discuss coursework, assignment and projects in real-time	3.05	1.12	ME	2.74	1.07	ME	2.90	1.10	ME
7	WhatsApp group is used for collaborative learning as it allows students and lecturers to access learning materials and communicate anytime and anywhere	2.66	1.06	ME	2.57	1.10	ME	2.62	1.08	ME
8	Students and lecturers can use WhatsApp group to learn, share educational files, audios and videos to make learning more interesting and lively	2.56	1.13	ME	2.70	1.08	ME	2.63	1.11	ME
9	WhatsApp group is used for collaborative learning as students can create as many groups as possible to aid their ideas, opinions and chat freely	2.84	1.09	ME	2.91	1.02	ME	2.88	1.06	ME
10	WhatsApp group allows for seamless collaboration and enhances teamwork, regardless of physical location	2.90	1.12	ME	2.83	1.20	ME	2.87	1.16	ME
	Grand Mean/ SD	2.29	0.88	ME	2.21	0.88	ME	2.25	0.88	ME

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

It would be observed from Table 3 that the mean ratings on every item describing the extent of usage of WhatsApp by students for collaborative learning range from 2.56 to 3.00 indicating moderate extent. Similarly, the grand mean for each group exceeds 2.00 while the aggregate grand mean is 2.25, still indicating moderate extent. In other words, postgraduate students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education collectively admit that WhatsApp group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities to a moderate extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent do Business Education Postgraduate Students use YouTube group for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities?

Table 4: Mean Ratings of Postgraduate students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the Extent to which YouTube group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students.

S/N	Items	N91								
		RSU (n = 44)			IAUE (n=47)			Aggregate		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
11	YouTube group is used for collaborative learning as group of students can create, share and watch educational videos from other universities across the globe	2.15	1.11	LE	2.65	0.90	ME	2.40	1.09	ME
12	YouTube group is used for collaborative learning as group of students understand complex theories through animation, diagrams and live demonstrations	2.23	0.96	LE	2.70	0.82	ME	2.47	0.89	ME
13	YouTube group is used for collaborative learning as group of students can review complex topics, revisit lectures and gain a better understanding of concept they may have missed in class	2.50	1.07	LE	2.53	1.01	LE	2.57	1.04	ME
14	YouTube group is used for collaborative learning as group of students access learning materials at any time, allowing them to learn at their own pace and convenience	2.29	1.06	LE	2.83	0.78	ME	2.56	0.92	ME
15	Students will get a better understanding watching videos of course topics taught which lead to interaction among students, thus facilitating collaborative learning through YouTube group	2.75	0.86	ME	2.96	0.66	ME	2.86	0.76	ME
Grand Mean/ SD		2.34	1.01	ME	2.71	0.83	ME	2.53	0.94	ME

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

The aggregate grand mean from table 4 above was 2.34 (SD = 1.01) for respondents from Rivers State University and 2.53 (SD=0.94) for Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. This suggests that all the respondents share the common opinion that YouTube group is used to a moderate extent, for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education.

Research Question 4: To what extent do Business Education Postgraduate Students of Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) use Twitter group for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities?

Table 5: Mean Ratings of Postgraduate Students on the Extent to which Twitter group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students

S/N	Items	N = 91								
		RSU (n = 44)			IAUE (n=47)			Aggregate		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
16	Twitter group is used for collaborative learning as group of students create their own classroom twitter group handle to tweet back and forth on educational information across the globe	3.12	0.30	HE	3.09	0.47	HE	3.11	0.89	HE
17	Twitter group is used for collaborative learning as it encourages group of students to summarize what they learnt because it forces them to condense their thought into 28 characters or less	3.23	0.33	HE	3.13	0.51	HE	3.18	0.42	HE
18	Twitter group is used for collaborative learning as it encourage group of students to learn from others on twitter and even share their knowledge with a global community	3.00	0.29	HE	3.10	0.53	HE	3.05	0.41	HE
19	Twitter group is used for collaborative learning as students and lecturers run out of ideas trying to make a class interactive "Twitter group for lecturers" and twitter group for students helps them access links and get insightful ideas from other lecturers and students around the world.	2.88	0.28	ME	2.78	0.47	ME	2.83	0.38	ME
20	Twitter group is used for collaborative learning as it helps students and lecturers to keep up with the current trending educational information, events, articles etc.	2.92	0.28	ME	2.87	0.47	ME	2.90	0.38	ME
Grand Mean/SD		3.03	0.30	HE	2.99	0.49	ME	3.01	0.50	HE

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

Table 5 revealed shows an item-by-item analyses of statements relating to the extent to which Twitter group is used for collaborative learning among postgraduate students of Universities in Rivers State. The result shows respective grand mean responses of 3.03 (SD = 0.30) and 2.99 (SD=0.49) for Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education indicating high and moderate extents. However,

the aggregate grand mean response was 3.01 (SD= 0.50) falling within the defined range of high extent. Thus, it could be concluded that students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education are of the same view that to a high extent, Twitter group is used for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the extent to which Facebook group is used for collaborative learning.

Table 6: t-test Analysis of Postgraduate Students Responses on the extent to which Facebook group is used for collaborative learning.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	Std Error	α	t _{calc.}	t _{crit.}	Decision
RSU	44	2.42	0.84	89	0.0405	0.05	1.23	1.98	Accept Ho
IAUE	47	2.47	0.71						

Source: Researchers Field Result, 2025

Table 6 shows an observed t-value of 1.23 against a critical t-value of 1.98 at the 0.05 level of significance when degrees of freedom is 89. shows an observed t-value of 1.23 against a critical t-value of 1.98 at the 0.05 level of significance when degrees of freedom is 89. The lesser computed t-value compared to the table suggests that the computed value is not significant at the 0.05 level of significance and hence the stated null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean ratings of Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University on the extent to which Facebook was used for collaborative learning, is retained. In other words, the confirms the earlier result that Business Education Postgraduate Students of both universities agree that Facebook group is used for collaborative learning to a moderate extent.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the extent to which WhatsApp group is used for collaborative learning.

Table 7: t-test Analysis of Postgraduate Students Responses on the extent to which WhatsApp group is used for collaborative learning.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	Std Error	α	t _{calc.}	t _{crit.}	Decision
RSU	44	2.29	0.88	89	0.0456	0.05	1.75	1.98	Accept Ho
IAUE	47	2.21	0.88						

Source: Researchers Field Result, 2025

In Table 7 it could be observed from the analysis that the calculated t-value of 1.75 is less than its critical equivalent of 1.98 and therefore insignificant at the 0.05 level of significance. In other words, the difference in mean ratings is not significant which confirms the stated null hypothesis and so it is retained. Therefore,

any other observed difference could be attributed to sampling error. By implications, the result of this tested null hypothesis is a confirmation of the finding in research question 2, that Postgraduate Business Education Students of Rivers State Universities use WhatsApp group for collaborative learning to a moderate extent.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the extent to which YouTube group is used for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities.

Table 8: t-test Analysis of Postgraduate Students Responses on the extent to which YouTube group is used for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	Std Error	α	t _{calc.}	t _{crit.}	Decision
RSU	44	2.54	1.01						
				89	0.0482	0.05	1.45	1.98	Accept Ho
IAUE	47	2.61	0.83						

Source: Researchers Field Result, 2025

From Table 8, the computed value of t is less than the table or critical value $\{t_{calc.} (1.45) < t_{crit.} (1.98)\}$. This implies that the calculated value is not significant at 0.05 alpha level with 89 degrees of freedom (df), and any other observed significant value can be attributed to chance, hence the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Postgraduate students on the extent to which YouTube group is used for collaborative learning.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) on the extent to which Twitter group is used for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities.

Table 9: t-test Analysis of mean rating of Postgraduate Students on the extent to which Twitter group is used for collaborative learning in Rivers State Universities.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	Std Error	α	t _{calc.}	t _{crit.}	Decision
RSU	44	3.03	0.30						
				89	0.0207	0.05	1.93	1.98	Accept Ho
IAUE	47	2.99	0.49						

Source: Researchers Field Result, 2025

It could be observed from the above table that the observed value of t is less than the critical equivalent, therefore the null hypothesis was retained. This means that the difference is too insignificant and any contrary observed value may be due to sampling error. The implication is that the two groups do not differ in their opinion as to the extent to which Twitter group is used for collaborative learning by Business Education Postgraduate students of Rivers State Universities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that Students of the Rivers State Universities agreed that Facebook group is used for collaborative learning to a moderate extent, among Business Education Postgraduate student. The t-test analyses conducted in respect of the observed values showed a lesser computed value against its critical equivalent which led to the rejection of the postulated null hypothesis. The result of the analyses strengthens the earlier finding that Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities utilized Facebook for collaborative learning to a moderate extent. Moreover, the result supports the positions of Aleksandrova and Parusheva (2019) that Facebook is one of the popular platforms used for learning support tools. It also corroborates the affirmation by Radwan et al. (2020), that the most widely used tool for academic-related communication is Facebook, and that it is the most commonly used social media platform among students, and has proven to be the most popular among students for its ease of use.

WhatsApp and YouTube were also found to be utilized for collaborative learning among Business Education Postgraduate Students to a moderate extent. All statistical tests and analyses conducted confirm this fact. This result attests to the assertions of Akpan and Ezinee (2017) who perceived WhatsApp as an educational tool with the potential of making learning interesting, just as Miguel, Adrian and Pelayo (2022) advanced that teachers and students through the use of YouTube can evaluate certain transversal competencies such as teamwork skills, oral expression, critical spirit and creativity among others.

Finally, the study revealed that Twitter group is used for collaborative learning to a high extent, among Business Education Postgraduate Students in Rivers State Universities. This finding agrees with Maite and Elena (2016) who posited that Twitter is a tool that encourages students' feedback, promote peer review and improves students' satisfaction and performance in various studies.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes the adaptation of Social Media Sites for collaborative learning helps student to interact, share ideas with colleagues and lecturers and facilitate students understanding and creativity; dynamic research-oriented and also enhanced in bridging academic gaps that hitherto occurred among students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The use of social media especially for collaborative learning should be highly encouraged.
2. Institutions of higher learning and other educational institutions as well as stakeholders in education should from time to time organize workshops and seminars on the use of social media for academic purposes.

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